

A NOVEL BIOREFINERY APPROACH USING EDIBLE ASCOMYCETE AND ZYGOMYCETE FILAMENTOUS FUNGI TO VALORIZE VINASSE FROM THE DISTILLERY INDUSTRY

Luziana Hoxha^{1,2,*}, Patrik R. Lennartsson², Matteo Marangon¹, Mohammad J. Taherzadeh²

¹ Department of Agronomy, Food, Natural Resources, Animals and Environment, University of Padova, 35020, Padova, Italy

² Swedish Centre for Resource Recovery, University of Borås, 50190 Borås, Sweden

* E-mail: luziana.hoxha@unipd.it

ABSTRACT: The growing global demand for sustainable protein sources—driven by population growth, climate change, and mounting pressure on conventional agriculture—has intensified interest in valorizing agri-food by-products. Among these, the wine and distillery industries offer substantial untapped potential for resource recovery from oenological by-products, presenting valuable opportunities to advance circular bioeconomy solutions. Post-distillation wine lees (vinasse), generated at up to 17 liters per liter of ethanol produced, represent a high-volume by-product that poses environmental and health risks due to the complex composition and high chemical oxygen demand. This study explores a novel biorefinery approach to biovalorize vinasse utilizing edible Ascomycete and Zygomycete filamentous fungi, specifically *Aspergillus oryzae*, *Rhizopus oryzae*, and *Neurospora intermedia*. Submerged fermentations were conducted at various vinasse concentrations (5–100% v/v), at 35 °C, 115 rpm, and pH 5, over 48–120 hours. Optimal fungal growth occurred at 10% (v/v) vinasse, with moderate growth at 5% and 15%, and no growth above 20%. The highest biomass yield was achieved within 48 to 72 hours by *Neurospora intermedia* and *Aspergillus oryzae*, and between 72 and 96 hours by *Rhizopus oryzae*. These findings demonstrate the effective bioconversion of vinasse into protein-rich fungal biomass, contributing to food system resilience and environmental sustainability.

Keywords: biorefinery, biobased products, circular economy, fermentation, proteins.

1 INTRODUCTION

The growing global demand for sustainable protein sources—driven by population growth, climate change, and increasing strain on conventional agriculture—has led to intensified interest in valorizing agri-food by-products. In this context, the wine industry, a key economic sector in the European Union, offers untapped potential for resource recovery from oenological by-products, thereby developing new solutions within circular bioeconomy.

In accordance with Regulation (EU) No 1308/2013 [1], wine producers are obliged to manage the by-products of winemaking or grape processing, typically by delivering them to distilleries for alcohol production. Traditionally, the residues remaining after distillation are commonly used as fertilizers, animal feed, or fuels. Nowadays, advanced technologies are enabling the development of innovative products from oenological by-products [2].

Ethanol production from wine lees generates substantial quantities of effluent—commonly known as vinasse—with up to 17 liters produced for every liter of ethanol [3]. This results in the generation of trillions of liters of vinasse annually, highlighting a critical need for sustainable management strategies.

Vinasses generated after the distillation of wine lees is a complex effluent characterized by a dark color, acidic pH (3.8–4.2), and a highly variable chemical composition. It contains high concentrations of organic matter (volatile solids: 32,200–152,700 mg/L), nutrients such as nitrogen (650–17,400 mg/L) and phosphorus (65–7,400 mg/L), as well as proteins (2,750–32,200 mg/L), lipids (250–12,250 mg/L), and minerals including potassium, calcium, magnesium, and trace metals [3].

Additionally, vinasse exhibits elevated biochemical and chemical oxygen demand (BOD₅: 16,300–67,500 mg/L; COD: 27,500–122,000 mg/L) and a significant solid content (36,600–171,500 mg/L) [3]. These high values are primarily attributed to the presence of sugars, proteins, organic acids, ethanol, glycerol, and high-molecular-weight compounds derived from grapes and wine—such as polyphenols, tannins, furans as 5-

hydroxymethyl furfural—which are resistant to biological degradation [4,5]. Thus if not properly managed, vinasse disposal can cause severe environmental damage, including soil and water contamination, alterations in soil physicochemical properties, salinization and sodification, eutrophication of aquatic systems, degradation of soil structure, unpleasant odors, and even inhibition of seed germination [6]. Given vinasse's seasonal production, chemical complexity, and variability, developing effective (bio)conversion strategies is essential to mitigate its negative environmental impacts.

Recently vinasse has garnered increasing attention for its valorization potential, particularly focused on biotechnological conversion into value-added products. In addition, it has been explored as a cost-effective substrate for growing a range of microorganisms [7,8], also for the production of filamentous fungi biomass and fungal metabolites [6,9].

While several studies have explored vinasse treatment and reuse, the integration into fungal fermentation systems of vinasse generated from distillation of wine lees remains limited. This study explores a novel bioconversion strategy for vinasse by employing edible Ascomycetes and Zygomycetes—specifically *Aspergillus oryzae*, *Rhizopus oryzae*, and *Neurospora intermedia*—to produce protein-rich fungal biomass. This valorization approach simultaneously addresses two pressing challenges: the need for sustainable protein sources and effective organic waste management. This dual-purpose innovation advances the concept of biorefineries by converting industrial waste into high-value products.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Substrate

Vinasse samples were provided by Acquavite Distillery (Vazzola, Italy) in December 2023. The vinasse was derived from the distillation process of wine lees, also known as post distillation wine lees. The vinasse samples were stored in a cold-room at 4 °C until further use.

Vinasse solutions were prepared at concentrations of

5-100% (v/v) and served as cultivation media. Before fungal cultivations all samples were sterilized at 121 °C for 20 minutes.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the distillation process using wine lees as feedstock, highlighting vinnasse as the primary liquid effluent generated. (Adapted from Vlyssides et al.[3]).

2.2 Fungi strains

Cultivation experiments were conducted using three edible filamentous fungal strains sourced from the Westerdijk Fungal Biodiversity Institute in the Netherlands: *Rhizopus oryzae* var. *delemar* (CBS 145940), *Aspergillus oryzae* var. *oryzae* (CBS 819.72), and *Neurospora intermedia* (CBS 131.92). Spores were preserved in on Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) plates, which contained 4 g/L potato extract (Sigma-Aldrich, Buchs, Switzerland), 20 g/L glucose (Fisher Scientific, Loughborough, UK), and 15 g/L agar (Sigma, Buchs, Switzerland).

2.3 Fungal cultivation

Cultivations were carried out in 250 mL baffled Erlenmeyer flasks, each inoculated with 2 mL of spore suspension per 100 mL of vinnasse solution (5-100%, v/v) (Tab. I).

Table I: Fungal cultivations conditions in vinnasse

Cultivation system	Shake flasks	
Working volume (mL)	100	
Temperature (°C)	35	
Agitation (rpm)	115	
pH	5	
Fungal strains	<i>Aspergillus oryzae</i> , <i>Neurospora intermedia</i> , <i>Rhizopus oryzae</i>	
Concentration (% v/v)	5 -100	10
Supplementation ^a	NS, S	Y
Incubation time (hours)	72-120	48- 96

^aNS: non-supplemented, S: supplemented with vitamins 1 mL/L and trace metals 10 mL/L, Y: yeast extract, 5 g/L.

Flasks were incubated in a water bath at 35 °C with shaking at 115 rpm for up to 120 hours. Vinnasse solutions were tested at concentrations of 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, 25%, 30%, 35%, 40%, 45%, 50%, and 100% (v/v). Cultivations were performed both without supplementation (NS) and with supplementation (S: 1 mL/L of a vitamin solution and 10 mL/L of a trace metal solution). Additionally, only the 10% vinnasse concentration was tested with the addition of 5 g/L yeast extract (Y), and cultivations were conducted over 96 hours.

To monitor metabolite dynamics, 2 mL samples were

collected at 24-hour intervals (0, 24, 48, 72, 96 and 120 hours) and then centrifuged for 10 minutes at 20,000 × g. The supernatant was then separated, filtered through 0.2 μm pore size filters, and stored at -20 °C for further analysis [6]. Metabolite dynamics were analyzed for glucose (Glu), acetic acid (Ace), glycerol (Gly), ethanol (EtOH), and a mixture of sugars (Sug Mix) using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), which consisted of a Waters 2695 separation module (Waters Corporation, USA). All experiments were conducted in duplicate.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Fungal cultivation on vinnasse

To investigate the potential of vinnasse—generated from the distillation of wine lees—as a substrate for producing fungal biomass suitable for food or feed, three edible filamentous fungi (*Aspergillus oryzae*, *Rhizopus oryzae*, and *Neurospora intermedia*) were cultivated using submerged fermentation. The original undiluted vinnasse sample (concentration 100%, v/v) provided by the distillery did not support fungal growth, likely due to its high organic load and potential presence of inhibitory compounds. No fungal growth was observed between 20% and 50% vinnasse concentrations either, suggesting a critical threshold of toxicity or nutrient imbalance. Optimal fungal growth occurred at 10% (v/v), while moderate growth was observed at 5% and 15% (v/v), indicating that vinnasse dilution is necessary for effective fungal cultivation.

3.2 Metabolite dynamics during fungal cultivation on vinnasse

The metabolite profiles of *Aspergillus oryzae*, *Neurospora intermedia*, and *Rhizopus oryzae* were analyzed to evaluate their suitability to utilize vinnasse cultivation media, under both supplemented (vitamin and trace metals) and non-supplemented conditions. Key metabolites tracked included glucose, mixed sugars, glycerol, acetic acid, and ethanol over a cultivation period of 120 hours at three vinnasse concentrations (5%, 10%, and 15% v/v).

Across fungal strains and cultivation conditions, distinct metabolic strategies have been observed in response to vinnasse media and to nutrient supplementations (Fig. 2). Fungi strains efficiently metabolized nutrients in vinnasse at 10% concentrations vinnasse following the order 10% > 5% > 15% (v/v).

Glucose uptake varied notably among the fungal strains and under different cultivation conditions. *Aspergillus oryzae* and *Neurospora intermedia* demonstrated rapid and complete glucose utilization during the first 24 hours, with maximal depletion observed by 72-96 hours at 5% and 10% (v/v) vinnasse, in both supplemented and non-supplemented conditions. The strong preference for glucose is consistent with its rapid entry into glycolysis [6].

Figure 2: Metabolite dynamics of *Neurospora intermedia*, *Aspergillus oryzae*, and *Rhizopus oryzae* cultivated over 120 hours in a) 5% vinasse, b) 15% vinasse, and c) 10% vinasse, also d) 10% vinasse over 72 hours, and e) 10% vinasse over 96 hours, under both non-supplemented (NS) and supplemented (S: vitamin and trace metal solution) conditions, at pH 5.0. Measured metabolites include glucose (Glu), acetic acid (Ace), glycerol (Gly), ethanol (EtOH), and a mixture of sugars (Sug Mix).

Aspergillus oryzae and *Neurospora intermedia* exhibited highly efficient and progressive consumption of both glucose and mixed sugars, achieving near-complete utilization (~100%) by 120 hours, under both supplemented and non-supplemented conditions. Although supplementation with vitamins and trace metals did not significantly influence the final sugar uptake, it appeared to enhance the metabolic rate during the early stages of cultivation, suggesting a facilitative role in initiating metabolic activity.

Among the tested strains, *Neurospora intermedia* consistently achieved complete glucose consumption across all vinasse concentrations (5–15% v/v) within 96 to 120 hours. This performance highlights its notable resilience to vinasse-associated stress and superior adaptability to increasing concentration levels.

In contrast, *Rhizopus oryzae* displayed a distinct pattern in sugar uptake, particularly during the early cultivation phase (24–48 hours), where glucose and mixed sugar consumption remained relatively low. However, extended cultivation and the presence of nutrient supplementation led to marked improvements by 120 hours, indicating a slower initial adaptation followed by robust metabolic engagement over time.

At the highest vinasse concentration tested (15% v/v), glucose metabolism was significantly hindered, with uptake initiating within the first 48 hours and reaching just 48–55% by 120 hours. Mixed sugar consumption also plateaued at this concentration, achieving only 67–72% uptake by 120 hours, consistent with the delayed glucose metabolism observed at vinasse concentrations higher than 10% (v/v). These results suggest that elevated vinasse concentrations may exert osmotic stress or contain excessive amounts of inhibitory compounds such as phenolics, furfurals, or heavy metals [5].

Supplementation with vitamins and trace metals slightly enhanced the utilization of glucose and mixed sugars, particularly at higher vinasse concentrations (15% v/v). This suggests that although the strain is intrinsically efficient at sugar metabolism, nutrient supplementation

may facilitate earlier onset of metabolic activity.

Glycerol consumption exhibited species-specific variation (Fig. 2). *Aspergillus oryzae* demonstrated the highest capacity for glycerol uptake, achieving complete consumption within 120 hours, regardless of vinasse concentration. This suggests that *A. oryzae* is highly efficient in utilizing glycerol. In contrast, *Neurospora intermedia* and *Rhizopus oryzae* showed comparatively moderate glycerol metabolism, reaching approximately 26% at 120 hours, potentially due to glucose repression or limited enzyme activity [6].

Variations in vinasse concentration (5%, 10%, and 15%) had no significant impact on glycerol metabolism across the studied species. However, a slight reduction in uptake at 15% vinasse suggests potential mild inhibitory effects or metabolic limitations at higher concentrations. Minor enhancement of glycerol metabolism was observed upon nutrient supplementation with vitamin and trace metal solution.

Acetic acid was rapidly and consistently consumed by *Neurospora intermedia* and *Rhizopus oryzae*, or volatilized during cultivations, reaching up to 65% reduction within the first 24 hours. By 120 hours, acetic acid was nearly depleted (>97%) in cultures grown on 5% and 10% vinasse, under both supplemented and non-supplemented conditions. Consumption at 15% vinasse was slower, reaching approximately 61% by 120 hours, indicating potential inhibitory effects at higher vinasse concentrations. *Aspergillus oryzae* exhibited weaker acetic acid metabolism compared to the other fungi, with consumption reaching up to 61% at 10% vinasse and significantly lower uptake (~37%) at 15% vinasse by 120 hours. Across all fungal strains, acetic acid consumption followed the trend 10% > 5% > 15% (v/v) vinasse, and supplementation with vitamin and trace metals had a slight enhancing effect on substrate utilization (Fig. 2). These results underscore a good metabolic preference for acetic acid across all fungal strains, suggesting that acetic acid serves as a good source of energy and carbon during fungal growth in vinasse, which is consistent with previous

studies [6].

Ethanol consumption patterns (Fig. 2) varied significantly depending on fungal strain, vinasse concentration, and nutrient supplementations. Across all conditions, ethanol concentrations initially increased during the first 24 hours of cultivation, following the order: *Rhizopus oryzae* > *Neurospora intermedia* > *Aspergillus oryzae*. This was followed by a gradual decline of up to 80% by 120 hours (*Neurospora intermedia*), with similar trends observed in 5% and 10% vinasse cultivation media. All fungal strains demonstrated a steady ethanol consumption over time, with enhanced performance under nutrient-supplemented conditions. These declining ethanol trends, suggest that ethanol may be re-assimilated as a carbon source or lost through evaporation. The most rapid ethanol consumption, observed between 72 and 96 hours across all strains, indicates a potential metabolic shift toward ethanol oxidation or secondary metabolite synthesis. In 15% vinasse cultivation media, ethanol production was only evident for *R. oryzae* during the early fermentation phase. By 120 hours, ethanol utilization reached 36% for *N. intermedia*, 30% for *A. oryzae*, and 25% for *R. oryzae*. The data indicate that ethanol consumption is highly strain-dependent, with *N. intermedia* exhibiting the most robust uptake and conversion efficiency, particularly under supplemented

conditions. The addition of vitamins and trace elements significantly accelerated ethanol assimilation between 48 and 72 hours, and higher overall ethanol removal by 120 hours. This enhancement is likely due to enhanced stress tolerance under high-vinasse environments. These findings align with previous reports, confirming that ethanol is initially produced and subsequently re-assimilated by filamentous fungi, supporting potential application in integrated biorefinery processes to enhance overall ethanol yields by filamentous fungi [6].

Overall, fungal growth performance was strongly influenced by vinasse concentration. While carbon availability is crucial, the presence of inhibitory substances or imbalanced nutrients in vinasse likely played a role in limiting growth at higher concentrations. This observation is consistent with previous findings on microbial cultivation on agro-industrial by-products [6,8,9].

Figure 3 illustrates the cultivation performance of *Aspergillus oryzae*, *Neurospora intermedia*, and *Rhizopus oryzae* cultivated in 10% (v/v) vinasse supplemented with yeast extract over a 96-hour period. The metabolic conversion efficiency of each strain was evaluated, with the resulting metabolite profiles offering insights into the metabolic pathways active during fungal growth.

Figure 3: Metabolite dynamics of a) *Neurospora intermedia*, b) *Aspergillus oryzae*, and c) *Rhizopus oryzae* cultivated in 10% vinasse supplemented with yeast extracts and cultivated at pH 5.0 from 48 to 96 hours. Measured metabolites include glucose (Glu), acetic acid (Ace), glycerol (Gly), ethanol (EtOH), and a mixture of sugars (Sug Mix).

Neurospora intermedia, demonstrated rapid consumption of glucose and mixed sugars, reaching 63% and 45%, respectively, within the first 24 hours, and nearly complete depletion by 96 hours (Fig. 3). Glycerol utilization was slower, with 13–31% consumed between 24 and 72 hours and reaching 43% by 96 hours. In contrast,

acetic acid was utilized more efficiently, with 68% consumed by 24 hours and up to 93% at the end of cultivation. Ethanol consumption was particularly, increasing from 44% by 24 hours to 89% by 96 hours—the highest among all tested fungal strains. These metabolite dynamics suggest that *N. intermedia* possesses

a broad substrate utilization capacity and demonstrates improved metabolic activity under yeast extract enriched conditions.

Aspergillus oryzae exhibited a consistent and progressive utilization of glucose and mixed sugars, reaching approximately 75% consumption by 48 hours and nearly complete depletion by 72 hours (Fig. 3). Glycerol utilization followed a clear trend, with 42% consumed by 24 hours and up to 88% depleted between 72 and 96 hours, indicating effective metabolism of glycerol during the mid to late cultivation stages. Acetic acid consumption began at 21% within the first 24 hours and increased to 51% by 96 hours, coinciding with moderate ethanol synthesis in the early stage and reaching 78%

ethanol utilization by 96 hours. The overall metabolic profile of *A. oryzae* suggests enhanced efficiency in 10% (v/v) vinasse cultivation media supplemented with yeast extract compared to non-supplemented conditions, highlighting the beneficial role in process optimization.

Rhizopus oryzae exhibited a delayed metabolic response during the initial fermentation stage compared to the other fungal strains, with glucose, mixed sugars, and glycerol approaching complete utilization by 72 hours (Fig. 3). Despite the slower start, *R. oryzae* demonstrated high efficiency in acetic acid and ethanol consumption, reaching 96% and 85%, respectively, by 96 hours—surpassing the other strains.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates the potential of vinasse—a problematic effluent from the wine and distillery industries—as a low-cost substrate for producing protein-rich fungal biomass. The results offer valuable insights into the metabolic profiles of three filamentous fungi—*Aspergillus oryzae*, *Neurospora intermedia*, and *Rhizopus oryzae*—during submerged fermentation on vinasse. All strains showed efficient utilization at 10% vinasse, while slower fermentation rates were observed at 5% and 15%.

Despite overall effectiveness, each strain exhibited distinct metabolic traits and substrate preferences. *Neurospora intermedia* emerged as a strong candidate for integrated bioprocessing due to its robust carbon assimilation and fermentation kinetics. *Aspergillus oryzae*, with its broad substrate uptake capacity, is well-suited for co-conversion processes involving multiple carbon sources. *Rhizopus oryzae*, though slower in early growth, demonstrated high fermentative potential in later stages, making it ideal for extended fermentation processes.

While vitamins and trace metals slightly improved fermentation performance, yeast extract significantly enhanced early-stage growth and accelerated metabolite utilization, highlighting its potential as an effective supplement for vinasse valorization and process optimization.

The present study findings indicate vinasse's viability as a substrate for filamentous fungi biovalorization, particularly for producing protein-rich fungal biomass. This valorization strategy aligns with circular bioeconomy principles and supports climate-smart food and feed solutions. Future research should focus on scaling up the process in bubble columns bioreactor.

6 REFERENCES

- [1] Regulation (EU) No 1308/2013. of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 December 2013 establishing a common organisation of the markets in agricultural products and repealing Council Regulations (EEC) No 922/72, (EEC) No 234/79, (EC) No 1037/2001 and (EC) No 1234/2007, Nov 8, 2024. <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2013/1308/2024-11-08>.
- [2] Hoxha L, Taherzadeh MJ, Marangon M. Sustainable repurposing of grape marc: Potential for bio-based innovations. *Waste Management*, 2025; 203:114871. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2025.114871>.
- [3] Vlyssides A, Barampouti E, Mai S, Stamatoglou A, Tsimas E. Alternative biological systems for the treatment of vinasse from wine. *Water science and technology Journal of the International Association on Water Pollution Research*, 2010, 62:2899–904. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2010.647>.
- [4] Sousa RMOF, Amaral C, Fernandes JMC, Fraga I, Semitela S, Braga F, et al. Hazardous impact of vinasse from distilled winemaking by-products in terrestrial plants and aquatic organisms. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 2019;183:109493. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2019.109493>.
- [5] Lorenzo-Santiago MA, Camacho-Ruiz RM, García-Hernández E, Rendón-Villalobos R, Rodríguez-Campos J, Contreras-Ramos SM. Conversion of residual sugars from vinasses to 5-Hydroxymethyl furfural (5-HMF) and phenolic compounds using ion exchange resins and thermal treatment. *Environmental Technology & Innovation*, 2023, 32:103354. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eti.2023.103354>
- [6] Karimi S, Mahboobi Soofiani N, Lundh T, Mahboubi A, Kiessling A, Taherzadeh MJ. Evaluation of Filamentous Fungal Biomass Cultivated on Vinasse as an Alternative Nutrient Source of Fish Feed: Protein, Lipid, and Mineral Composition. *Fermentation*, 2019, 5(4):99. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fermentation5040099>.
- [7] Candido C, Lombardi AT. The physiology of *Chlorella vulgaris* grown in conventional and biodigested treated vinasses. *Algal Research*, 2018; 30:79–85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.algal.2018.01.005>.
- [8] Nair RB, Taherzadeh MJ. Valorization of sugar-to-ethanol process waste vinasse: A novel biorefinery approach using edible ascomycetes filamentous fungi. *Bioresour Technol*. 2016; 221:469–76. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2016.09.074>.
- [9] Nitayavardhana S, Issarapayup K, Pavasant P, Khanal SK. Production of protein-rich fungal biomass in an airlift bioreactor using vinasse as substrate. *Bioresource Technology*, 2013; 133:301–6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2013.01.073>.

7 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was funded by the European Commission, Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme, Grant Agreement No. 101105437, project BionovFOOD, and Swedish Research Council FORMAS Grant No. 2023-02018.